

Language as a Means for Communication and Cultural Reality Disclosure: Exploring the Nexus between Language and Culture

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Abstract

Language serves as a fundamental tool for communication, intricately intertwined with culture in its expression and reception. This paper delves into the symbiotic relationship between language and cultural reality, exploring how language encapsulates and expresses cultural nuances. It begins by examining the nature of language, its inherent characteristics, and its role as a communication device. Through various linguistic theories, it navigates the multifaceted functions of language in societal interactions. Furthermore, the paper elucidates the profound link between communication, language, and culture, highlighting how culture shapes language and vice versa. Drawing from anthropological and linguistic perspectives, it underscores how language reflects cultural norms, values, and beliefs. The Sapir-Whorf hypothesis is explored, elucidating how language influences perception and thought patterns, thereby shaping cultural realities. Moreover, the essence of culture is examined through diverse definitions, emphasizing its pervasive influence on human life. Culture encompasses language, customs, social organization, and various other elements that define societal existence. The paper emphasizes that language serves as a cultural reality discloser, embodying the intricacies of cultural experiences and perceptions. Through a comprehensive analysis of language and culture, the paper underscores their inseparable nature, likening their relationship to Siamese twins or two sides of a coin. It concludes by affirming that language not only reflects cultural realities but also actively shapes and perpetuates them. Thus, understanding the symbiosis between language and culture is crucial for comprehending human communication and societal dynamics.

Keywords: Language, Communication, Cultural reality, Sapir-Whorf hypothesis, Culture, Sociolinguistics

Introduction

A common proverb posits that language signifies the essence of a nation. When pondered deeply, this saying may enhance our understanding of the intricate connections between language and the behaviors or attitudes of its speakers (Alwi, 2004). Wisdom strengthens the belief in the critical role of language in cultural development.

Several theories discuss the relationship between language and culture. Some suggest that language is a part of culture, while others argue that although distinct, they are closely related and inseparable. Another perspective posits that language significantly influences culture, reflecting all cultural aspects. Conversely, some theories propose that culture influences language, shaping human thinking and perception. This paper intends to discuss the nature of language, the nature of culture, and how language can express the cultural reality of its users.

Language as a system, which means that formed by a number of components that are fixed and can be patterned. As a system, in addition to the systematic language are also systemic. Systematic meaning, language arranged according to a certain pattern, not arranged randomly or arbitrarily. While systematic means that language is a single system, but rather consists of several subsystems that differ from other languages. Language subsystem consists of phonology, morphology, syntax, and lexicon. Therefore, the language also commonly considered unique but universal at the same time. Unique means having the characteristics or properties not possessed by other languages, while universal means having the same traits that exist in all languages.

When compared with animals that have a variety of forms of communication, so people just use the language. There are two types of animal communication systems: first, communication systems found in the bees. The second all communication systems exist in monkeys and birds. Human languages have something similar to this communication, but has a major difference compared to both (Gee, 1993: 2). Bees can communicate the presence of nectars to their group members, like the distance of the nectars, direction to the location, and the number of nectar found by using a particular dance. Gee called the bee dance to communicate the presence of the nectar as point-by-point system. In addition to bees, monkeys and birds also have a way to communicate. Vervet African apes are capable to produce 36 kinds of sound for various situations. Among them was a different sound for the same situation, so vervet communication system able to deliver 22 kinds of messages. In addition, the birds also have a way to communicate even only consist of a very limited vocabulary to deliver messages. Furthermore, Chaer and Agustina (2004:26-29) suggests 16 kinds of distinctive human language, as follows:

- 1) The language uses vowel auditory pathway. In this case, there are similarities between communication systems owned by many animals, including crickets, frogs, and birds.
- 2) Language can be spread in all directions; yet receptions are directed. Spoken language sounds can be heard in all directions due to noise or sounds of language that propagates through the air, but the receiver or listener can tell exactly from which direction the sounds of language came.

- 3) The language symbol in the form of sound that can be disappear once pronounced. This is in contrast with another symbol, such as the footprints of animals and heroic statues that can last for long time. Because of the rapid loss, people always trying to preserve this symbol of language sounds into written form and sound recordings.
- 4) Participants in the communication with language can communicate to each other. This means that a speaker can be a symbol sender and as symbol recipient at the same time.
- 5) The language symbol can be a complete feedback. The speaker as the sender can hear their own language symbols. Whereas, in some kinetic communication (movement) and visual (sight) as the bee dance, the sender information is not able to see the important parts of the dance.
- 6) Communication languages has its own specialty. Humans can talk without having to do physical movements to support the communication process. Whereas communication in bees they physically forced to dance in order to deliver messages they intended to
- 7) Sound symbols in communication language means and refers to certain things. For example the word of horse refers to a type of quadrupeds that can be ridden. Sentence “Chaedar kick the ball” mean someone named Chaedar doing actions that hit the ball with his leg.
- 8) The relationship between language symbol with its meaning is not determined by the presence of a bond between the two, but is determined by agreement or convention between the speakers of the language
- 9) language as a tool of human communication can be separated into certain unit, i.e sentences, words, morphemes, and phonemes
- 10) Reference or something being discussed in the language not always be at the present place and time. Human language can be used for something in the past, in the future, or are in distant places. Even that only in fantasy
- 11) Language is open. It means, symbols of speech can be made according to the human needs. While the language of animals is closed, unchanged from the first.
- 12) Skill and finesse to master the rules and customs of human language derived from learning process, not through genes inborn. Animal language generally be congenital
- 13) The language can be learned. Someone who was born and raised in a particular language community will be able to learn other languages that not used in their community.
- 14) Language can be used to express the true and not true, or logically meaningless. Humans can use language to say the right things and that is not true. Only people who can use language to lie or deceive others.
- 15) Language has two subsystems namely the sound subsystem and meaning subsystems that enable language to have economic function. The economics diverse occurred by functional sound units that can be grouped and regrouped into meaningful units, e.g. phonemes into words.
- 16) The language can be used to talk about language itself.

The Nature of Language

Various definitions of language have been proposed by linguists. For instance, Chaer (1995) suggests that language is a form, not a substance, characterized by a symbolic sound system that is arbitrary, productive, dynamic, diverse, and humane. Language is systematic and consists of fixed, patterned components forming subsystems such as phonology, morphology, syntax, and lexicon, making it both unique and universal.

Human languages are distinguished from animal communication systems by their complexity and functionality (Gee, 1993). For example, bees use dances to communicate the location and quantity of nectar, while vervet monkeys produce specific sounds for different situations. Human languages, however, have unique characteristics such as auditory pathways, directional sound reception, ephemeral sound symbols, and the ability to express abstract and hypothetical ideas.

Language Functions

Traditionally, language is viewed as a tool for interaction and communication, conveying thoughts, ideas, concepts, and emotions. Sociolinguistics expands this view, considering language activities as encompassing "who speaks what language to whom, when, and to what end" (Chaer & Agustina, 2004).

From the speaker's perspective, language serves as a personal identity marker, expressing emotions and viewpoints (Jakobson). For listeners, language functions as a directive tool, regulating behavior and actions (Halliday). Additionally, language serves interactional purposes, maintaining communication and social relationships (Finnocchiaro & Halliday).

According to Pranowo in Halliday (1996), language functions can be classified into seven categories: instrumental, regulatory, representational, interactional, heuristic, personal, and imaginative. Cook (1989) further divides language functions into macro functions (e.g., emotive, directive, phatic) and micro functions, illustrating the varied communicative roles of language.

Traditionally it is stated that language is a tool to interact or tools to communicate, in a sense, means to convey thoughts, ideas, concepts, or even a feeling. The concept that language is a tool to convey the thought has had a long history. However, in the sociolinguistic thought considered to be too narrow because the language activity is basically a "who speak what language to Whom, when, and to what end." Therefore, from the view of sociolinguistics, language functions can be viewed from different angles, such as speakers, listeners, topics, codes, and conversation purpose (Chaer and Agustina, 2004: 15).

From the point of speaker, language serves as a personal or private identity and Jakobson called it as emotive function. It means, speakers expressed their stand point on what they speak out. The speakers not only express emotions through language, but also showed emotion when delivering their speech. Therefore, the listener can understand whether the speakers in an angry, sad, or happy.

From the point of the listener and the speaker, the language has a function as a directive, which regulate the behavior of the listener, and Halliday defines as instrumental function, while Jakobson called rhetorical. From this angle, the language not only makes the listener to do something, but the activities were consistent with what the speaker wants. This can

be done by the speakers through sentences that express a command, direction, demand, or seduction.

From the contact angle of the speaker and listener, the language has a fatigue function, Finocchiaro called it as interpersonal and Halliday called it as interactional. Despite Pranowo in Halliday (1996:63) also classify the function of language based on the concept beyond the language function as other experts do. They classify into seven functions as follows:

- 1) instrumental function is the function of the language used to manipulate the environment that led to a particular situation.
- 2) regulatory function is the use of language that serves to control an event, such as approval, rejection, etc.
- 3) the representational function of language that serves to make a statement, present the facts, etc.
- 4) the use of interactional function of language serves to maintain the relationship in order to keep communications running smoothly, delivering jokes, master jargon, idioms used by the particular conversational partner.
- 5) heuristic function is the function of the language that is used to acquire knowledge in order to recognize the environment, such as a child wondering about what is seen.
- 6) personal function, namely the use of language that serves to express feelings, emotions, personality, etc.
- 7) The function of the imaginative use of language that serve to create a system or be imaginative ideas.

While Guy Cook in Pranowo (1989:94) developed a classification of language functions into two, namely the macro and micro functions. Macro functions are classified into seven as Halliday did, namely:

- 1) Emotive function, for example: the expression "mad", "great", "ouch", etc.
- 2) Directive function, for example: "Help me please", "Shoot him!".
- 3) Phatic function is when speaker going to start a conversation such as: "Can you hear me!".
- 4) Referential function of language is to convey information.
- 5) Metalinguistic function is the usage of language that focuses on the code itself.
- 6) Poetic function is the usage of language by selecting the form that contains the essence of the message, for example, one ad shows how powerful dairy companies exploiting the potential of the poetic function of language: Cheddar : "Cheddar also want to go to school, Mom!" Mother: "Yeah, you will when you're growing, son!" Cheddar : "What can make me grow quickly Mom?" Mother: "Drinking the best milk, son!"

7) Contextual function is the usage of language to create different types of communication, for example, "Good! Let's start this exercise!". While micro function is communicative forms of each category of macro functions.

Language as a Communication Device

Language, as a means of communication, plays a crucial role among its speakers. It serves as a tool for self-expression, social interaction, and the conveyance of cultural identity (Keraf, 1997). Effective communication requires both the sender and receiver to master the language, ensuring clear and meaningful exchanges.

Language reflects a person's education level, social standing, and authority, influencing their interaction with others. It also serves legal, commercial, and social purposes, showcasing the multifaceted role of language in human society.

The Relationship between Communication, Language, and Culture

The link between communication and culture is evident in daily interactions. Culture influences language use, shaping communication practices, social actions, and perceptions (Porter & Samovar, 2006). Consequently, communication and culture are inseparable, with cultural diversity leading to varied communication practices.

The link between communication and culture, could be seen from our daily practice of communication or interaction between individuals and groups. The language we use must have been influenced by where we live, as well as the ethnic neighborhoods around us.

In this case, culture in regard to human being way of life. Humans learn, think, feel, believe, and seek what is appropriate according to the culture. Language, friendship, custom, practice communication, social action, economic activity, politics, and technology, all these were based on cultural patterns. As for who speak Makassarese, Gorontaloese, Sundanese, Javanese, Malay, and English. This is all because they have been born or at least raised in a culture that contains these elements. What they do, how they act, a response to cultural functions. (Porter & Samovar in Mulyana and Grace, 2006).

This means that communication and culture cannot be separated, because culture not only determines who is talking whom, about what, and where the communication takes place, but the culture also helped determine the encode messages, the meaning and the message he had for the conditions to send, pay attention, interpret the message. Actually, the whole repertoire of behavior we are very dependent on, the culture we grew up, in line with previously disclosed at the beginning of the discussion. Consequently, culture is the foundation of communication. If cultural diversity, it is also a variety of communication practices.

The Essence of Culture

Culture encompasses all aspects of human life, including language, technology, social organization, knowledge, religion, and art (Koentjaraningrat, 1974). Kroeber and Kluckhorn (1952) categorize cultural definitions into descriptive, historical, normative, psychological, structural, and genetic, highlighting the pervasive influence of culture on human existence.

Culture regulates societal behavior, provides a framework for learning and adaptation, and facilitates communication and cooperation (Nababan, 1984). Thus, culture is integral to human life, influencing all activities and interactions.

There are various definitions of culture are very different, and it could be true, or it could be considered incomplete. This difference occurs because the compilers usually see the cultural definition in terms of different aspects.

Koentjaraningrat (1974: 217) explains that culture only humans possess, and grow along with the development of human society. For that Koentjaraningrat using something he calls "cultural framework", which has two aspects, namely the form of culture and cultural content. Referred to as a form of culture is either: (1) a form of ideas (cultural system), which is abstract, (2) behavior (social systems), which are rather concrete, and (3) a physical or objects, which are universal, meaning the seventh element in every society there are people in the world. The seven elements are: (1) language, (2) technology system, (3) livelihood systems, (4) social organization, (5) knowledge of the system, (6) religious system, (7) art.

Kroeber and Kluckhorn in Pranowo (1952:86) has collected dozens of definitions of culture, and breaks it down into six categories according to the nature of the definition, namely: (1) a descriptive definition, the definition that emphasizes the elements of culture, (2) historical definition, the definition emphasizes that culture inherited social, (3) the definition of normative definitions emphasize the nature of culture as a rule of life and conduct. On the usefulness of culture in conformity with the environment, solving problems, and learn to live, (5) structural definition, the definition that emphasizes the nature of culture as a system patterned and orderly, (6) the genetic definition, the emphasis on the definition of culture as the work of man.

Based on the grouping of the above it can be seen that culture pervades all aspects and dimensions of human life. It can be said that any human activity with all the results and the result is included in the concept of culture. Grouping cultural definitions made Nababan (1984) also showed that culture covers all aspects and elements of human life. Nababan cultural definition classifies into four categories, namely (1) the definition of a view of culture as a regulator and tie the community, (2) the definition of a view of culture as the things that man has acquired through learning or education (nurture), (3) the definition of a view the customs and culture of human behavior, and (4) the definition of a view of culture as a system of communication that people use to gain cooperation, unity, and survival of human society.

Based on the above in other words it can be said that culture is everything that concerns human life, including the rules or applicable law in society, the results of manmade, custom

and tradition are wont to do, and as well as the interaction or communication tool used, the language and tools of communication is non-verbal.

Language as a Cultural Reality Discloser

Different theories explore the relationship between language and culture. Some argue that language is a part of culture, while others view them as distinct yet interconnected. Language reflects cultural realities, influencing thought patterns and perceptions (Cahyono, 1995).

According to the Sapir-Whorf hypothesis, language shapes perception and thought, depicting a symbolic world unique to its users (Whorf). This theory suggests that language influences how individuals perceive and interact with their environment, as illustrated by the numerous words Eskimos have for snow, or the diverse terms in classical Arabic for camels.

Conclusion

Language and culture are intricately linked, each influencing and shaping the other. Language reflects cultural norms, values, and beliefs, while culture shapes language use and development. Understanding this symbiotic relationship is crucial for comprehending human communication and societal dynamics. Language not only reflects but also perpetuates cultural realities, highlighting its role as a fundamental tool for communication and cultural expression.

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